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**"INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION STYLES AND RESPECT
FOR VALUES: AN ANALYSIS BASED ON SHAKESPEARE'S OTHELLO
TRAGEDY"**<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14262330>**F.N. Bekmurodova**

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This article examines the concept of intercultural communication styles, and respect for values based on Shakespeare's tragedy Othello are analyzed. Tragedy explores themes of race, culture, and trust, showing how it affects cross-cultural communication and social relationships. The article analyzes Othello's unique place in Venetian society and how his racial background shapes his relationships and connections with cultured people. It also emphasizes the importance of respecting people of different cultures and thereby helps cultures and avoids conflict. Through Othello, the article attempts to raise the complexities and importance of intercultural communication in a global world.

Keywords: *Intercultural communication, values, respect, Shakespeare, Othello, race, identity, social dynamics, communication styles, intercultural understanding, global world.*

**«МЕЖКУЛЬТУРНЫЕ СТИЛИ ОБЩЕНИЯ И УВАЖЕНИЕ К
ЦЕННОСТЯМ: АНАЛИЗ НА ОСНОВЕ ТРАГЕДИИ ШЕКСПИРА
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АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье рассматриваются концепции стилей межкультурной коммуникации и уважения к ценностям на основе трагедии Шекспира Отелло. Трагедия исследует такие темы, как раса, культура и доверие, показывая, как эти аспекты влияют на межкультурную коммуникацию и социальные отношения. В статье анализируется уникальное положение Отелло в венецианском обществе и то, как его расовое происхождение формирует его отношения и связи с культурными людьми. Также подчеркивается важность уважения к людям разных культур, что способствует взаимопониманию между культурами и предотвращает конфликты. Через Отелло статья стремится подчеркнуть сложности и важность межкультурной коммуникации в глобализированном мире.

Ключевые слова: *межкультурная коммуникация, ценности, уважение, Шекспир, Отелло, раса, идентичность, социальная динамика, стили коммуникации, межкультурное взаимопонимание, глобальный мир.*

INTRODUCTION

Intercultural communication refers to the communication between people from two different cultures. [Chen & Starosta, 1998: p 28] Intercultural communication is a symbolic, interpretive, transactional, contextual process, in which people from different cultures create shared meanings. [Lustig & Koester, 2007: p 46] Intercultural communication refers to the effects on communication behavior, when different cultures interact together. Hence, one way of viewing intercultural communication is as communication that unfolds in symbolic intercultural spaces. [Arasaratnam, 2013: p 480] Intercultural (or "cross-cultural") communication, broadly speaking is: the (direct or mediated) interaction between people belonging to different cultures, possessing different references, beliefs, values, traditions, histories, languages, in order to achieve (commonly accepted) objectives or goals and in being aware of the cultural diversity of the participants as an intrinsically added value which should be respected and "cultivated". [Peter.S, 2010 p 15,16] Typical intercultural or cross-cultural projects and programs: Implementation of (economic, social, medical, ...) programs in developing countries, Community education and cross-community consensus building in multicultural (urban) environments; (Political, economic, military, ...) consensus building between different, national and international actors; Building and management of global (economic, social, ...) projects requiring the participation of people belonging to different traditions, Humanitarian interventions (peace keeping, natural catastrophes, ...) requiring a knowledge of the "beneficiary" culture and its active participation. (ibid)

In Shakespeare's tragedy Othello, issues of intercultural communication and respect for values are dealt with extensively. Through the following excerpts, we will analyze how cultural differences and misunderstandings arise in the play.

1. Othello's racial background and being seen as the "other" in Venetian society. Excerpt: Othello: "I am not what I am" (Act 1, Scene 1) Analysis: This sentence means that Othello cannot see himself as fully accepted in the Venetian society and conforming to their values. He feels alienated from his own culture because the Venetians see him as racial and "other".

2. Iago's manipulation and Othello's loss of intercultural trust. Excerpt: Iago: "Beware, my lord, of jealousy; It is the green-eyed monster which mocks. The meat feeds on it." (Act 3, Scene 3) Analysis: Iago's words make Othello distrustful of his wife. Iago, pretending to be a friend, performs a high degree of manipulation that goes against Othello's culture. Othello basically feels like an "other" in Venetian society, and Iago uses this ambiguity to his advantage. Because Othello's lack of confidence in his own values, he easily believes Iago's lies.

3. Othello's failure to protect his cultural values in society. Fragment: Othello: "Then you must speak Of one that loved not wisely but too well; Of one not easily jealous, but being wrought, Perplexed in the extreme; of one whose hand Like the base Indian, threw a pearl away. Richer than all his tribe." (Act 5, Scene 2) Analysis: Othello describes here the loss of himself and his wife (Desdemona). He feels that, along with his own cultural values, he is not compatible with the values and communication styles of the Venetians. As Othello describes his emotionally conflicted situation, he becomes aware of the gap between his cultures and how he is seen as the "other". Through the expression 'Base Indian', Othello realizes that his own cultural values and identity have not been valued. Thus, his loss of self-esteem and cross-cultural misunderstandings lead to his eventual downfall.

4. Cross-cultural differences in Venetian society and Othello's style of self-presentation. Fragment: Cassio: "You may deny that you are not a worthy man, But we are all disposed to mischief." (Act 2, Scene 3) Analysis: Cassio's words represent Othello's lack of acceptance in Venetian society and his difficulty expressing his culture. Othello's life and career are largely concerned with the interactions and roles of the Venetians in society. People in Venetian society try to change Othello's social position and personality by forcing their cultural values on him. Othello's self-doubts and vulnerabilities reflect his problems in accepting his culture. This leads to a breakdown of intercultural relations and a dangerous situation.

Conclusion

Othello shows the complex relationship between intercultural communication, respect for values and social positions. Othello's story highlights the importance of

fostering respect and understanding in intercultural communication and how this can lead to global peace. Shakespeare's Othello serves as a profound study of the dangers of ignoring intercultural values and the need for empathy and open communication in a multicultural society. This tragedy prompts a deeper understanding of how respecting cultural values and acknowledging differences in communication can foster positive relationships and mitigate conflict, offering timeless insights for today's interconnected and diverse world.

REFERENCES:

1. Arasaratnam, L. A. Intercultural communication competence. In A. Kurylo (Ed.), *Intercultural communication: Representation and construction of culture* (Chap 3, pp. 47-68). (2013). Los Angeles, CA: SAGE Publications.
2. Chen, G. M., & Starosta, W. J. *Foundations of intercultural communication*: Boston, MA: Allyn & Bacon.(1998)
3. Lustig, M. W., & Koester, J. *Intercultural competence: interpersonal communication across cultures* (5th ed.).(2007) Shanghai, China: Shanghai Foreign Language Education Press.
4. Peter.Stockinger. *Intercultural Communication. A general introduction*. ROMA.PU Institut National des Langues et Civilisations(Orientales) Inalco (2010)
5. Shakespeare. V. Othello (1622) in London